

What is rural abandonment and why we should care about it

Some basic data

LARGE DISPROPORTION IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE TERRITORY BETWEEN RURAL AND URBAN POPULATIONS

Migration to cities due to lack of economic opportunities, jobs, basic services and infrastructure.

Rural abandonment, particularly the abandonment of traditional agriculture, refers to the process by which people and economic activities move from rural to urban areas, leaving traditional farmlands without management. This phenomenon occurs for a variety of reasons, such as a lack of economic opportunities in the countryside, migration to cities in search of work, scarcity of services, and basic infrastructure.

Rural areas have developed through the interaction and management of local populations, generating areas with strong linkages between natural ecosystems and culture. Therefore, some rural areas represent areas with high levels of biodiversity and cultural diversity, exemplifying areas of sustainable land management.

Biocultural diversity highlights the links among biological, linguistic, and cultural diversity. Biocultural diversity recognizes that the interaction between nature and local populations can generate high biodiversity and cultural diversity values, fostering sustainable systems.

Sayings and proverbs

Owing to the close relationship between people and natural ecosystems, the rural environment can represent a space where biocultural diversity can be maintained and conserved. Traditional agriculture is an example of this, since traditional agricultural practices have shaped the territory, fostering areas with high biodiversity values where traditions, knowledge, and traditional knowledge are linked to the territory.

Implications of rural abandonment

Rural abandonment can present opportunities for renaturalization, increasing biodiversity, and contributing to ecosystem restoration. However, it also presents a major problem because of its economic, social, and environmental implications.

Economic: it can lead to a decrease in agricultural production, which would negatively affect the local and national economy and food security.

Sociocultural: contributes to the depopulation of rural areas, which has a negative impact on culture, knowledge, and traditions. Rural abandonment has an important impact on the quality of life of local populations through the loss of local identity and sense of place, cultural heritage, ecological cultural heritage, and local ecological knowledge.

Ecological: can cause soil degradation and biodiversity loss, negatively affecting the environment and sustainability.

Traditional agriculture and rural areas as refugia for the conservation of biocultural diversity.